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Trophoectoderm differentiation guided by Xist.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

Citations

1. Chitiashvili, T., Dror, I., Kim, R., Hsu, F.M., Chaudhari, R., Pandolfi, E., Chen, D., Liebscher, S., Schenke-Layland, K., Plath, K. and Clark, A., 2020. Female human primordial germ cells display X-chromosome dosage compensation despite the absence of X-inactivation. Nature cell biology, 22(12), pp.1436-1446.